

KOALA Diamond Open Access Service Agreement for a National Contact Point

between

GERMAN INSTITUTION

represented by: [REDACTED]

seated at: [REDACTED]

(hereinafter individually referred to as “KOALA consortium”)

and

FOREIGN INSTITUTION

represented by: [REDACTED]

seated at: [REDACTED]

(hereinafter individually referred to as “NCP”)

(hereinafter individually and collectively referred to as "Party(ies)")

Introduction of the GERMAN INSTITUTION, including a description of the institution, with particular emphasis on activities in the field of Diamond Open Access and of the KOALA-model. The following is an example:

The KOALA funding model facilitates collective funding of Diamond Open Access journals and platforms in a transparent and sustainable model. KOALA – a German acronym translating to “Establishing Consortial Open Access Solutions” – established consortial solutions for financing open access by collaboratively funding OA journals and book series by academic libraries, research institutions, associations, and companies. It provides an alternative to the dominant APC model, where articles are paid for individually by authors or their institutions. The KOALA funding model provides fair and sustainable funding for quality-assured APC-free open access publications (“Diamond Open Access”). It reduces financial barriers for authors and thus facilitates participation in OA publications. Consortial financing is thus a science-friendly alternative to author-facing publishing and an essential part of a vibrant OA culture.

Introduction of NCP.

1. Subject of the Cooperation

This cooperation aligns the missions of both the KOALA consortium and NCP to advance Diamond Open Access in an equitable, sustainable, and globally connected way, demonstrated by the approach of collective funding. Together, the Parties want to support a broader community of institutions that value transparent and community-driven Diamond Open Access publishing. Joint communication efforts will emphasize a transparent, community-led approach to ensure maximum visibility and trust within research and library communities.

The cooperation seeks to extend KOALA's innovative model into NCP's area by leveraging NCP's infrastructure, community network and experience with Open-Access-Consortia. It shall encourage global support for Diamond Open Access and enable cross-continental collaboration to sustainably fund scholarly communication.

2. Scope of Cooperation: KOALA National Contact Point (NCP)

- 2.1.** NCP is listed as a participant in the specific consortial KOALA offer. Therefore, KOALA consortium and NCP will conclude an agreement on participation in the specific consortial KOALA offer.
- 2.2.** NCP shall be the KOALA National Contact Point (NCP) for AREA and shall thus cover for KOALA consortium:
 - 2.2.1.** Institutions in the AREA
 - 2.2.2.** (OPTIONALLY) OTHER AREAS
- 2.3.** For the avoidance of doubt, any other Institutions – not covered by 2.2. of this agreement – shall not be accepted by NCP for participation in consortial KOALA offers.
- 2.4.** For the avoidance of doubt, KOALA consortium will not cooperate with other institutions for regions or institutions covered by 2.2. of this Agreement.
- 2.5.** The NCP shall
 - 2.5.1.** represent the offers of KOALA consortium within their network,
 - 2.5.2.** administrate the pledges of the institutions,
 - 2.5.3.** Promote KOALA consortium's offers through its existing networks, events, newsletters, and other appropriate channels,
 - 2.5.4.** determine a fundamental pricing mode by NCP in agreement with KOALA consortium, therefore NCP may adjust prices in specific cases when compelling reasons arise,
 - 2.5.5.** choose not to provide KOALA consortium's offers, if conflicts arise without consensus with KOALA consortium,
 - 2.5.6.** keep informed about participating institutions, their financial contributions, deducted fees and commission,
 - 2.5.7.** provide biweekly updates on pledge status to KOALA consortium.

3. Scope of cooperation: KOALA consortium

- 3.1.** KOALA consortium will provide the NCP with detailed information on its offers, including financial needs, publication data, contact persons, the tiering of KOALA consortium's own offers and context of agreements.
- 3.2.** An offer of KOALA consortium comprises at least one scientific journal that will be funded in a collective funding model for three years, following the initial pledging year.

4. Financial Terms

- 4.1.** Together, KOALA consortium & NCP will develop a flexible banding/tiering model for institutions, with pricing based on institutional size, capacity, and interest, while considering country-specific conditions.
- 4.2.** NCP may add commission up to X% on successful contributions or memberships secured via its outreach and administrative services from the contributors.

- 4.3. All agreements on participation and cooperation regarding KOALA consortium's offers must run for the offer's whole duration (in general: three years (per the current consortial model)).
- 4.4. For each offer, in case of successful pledging by NCP,
 - 4.4.1. NCP and KOALA consortium shall sign a participation agreement that includes a payment obligation (2.1.). The Parties agree on the euro as their currency.
 - 4.4.2. annual invoices by KOALA consortium will be followed accordingly by annual payments by NCP.
- 4.5. Starting one year after the Agreement's initiation, KOALA consortium and NCP will conduct a joint review of past achievements and future plans annually.
- 4.6. For the avoidance of doubt, Each Party shall bear its own costs incurred in the implementation of this Agreement.

5. Marketing

- 5.1. The Parties will mutually assist each other in marketing campaigns and provide information material on the supplied data.
- 5.2. Each Party is entitled to use the name of the other Party exclusively for marketing purposes. Any other use of the name of the other Party shall in each case require an express written consent.

6. Contact Person

- 6.1. The designated contact persons for all correspondence between NCP and KOALA consortium in relation to this Agreement shall be:
For NCP: XX
FOR KOALA consortium: XX
- 6.2. Should one of the contact persons change, the leaving person will introduce a replacement in due time to the other contacts.

7. Term

- 7.1. This Agreement will commence on **XX/start date**.
- 7.2. Either Party may terminate it at any time. In such an event, all ongoing operations should be concluded in an orderly manner. All existing agreements on collective funding need to be followed through.

8. Data protection/data security

- 8.1. The Contracting Parties shall comply with the applicable rules and regulations on data protection and data security (in particular the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Lower Saxony Data Protection Act (NDSG) and the German Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG). Each Contracting Party shall be responsible for the lawful processing of any personal data. In particular if third Parties are involved, e.g., through the use of external software etc., processing agreements may have to be obtained. The Contracting Parties shall inform each other thereof.
- 8.2. To the extent that the Contracting Parties, in the course of this project, jointly process personal data within the meaning of Art. 26 GDPR, they shall enter into a joint controller agreement within the meaning of Art. 26 GDPR.

8.3. In the event that personal data is transferred to countries outside the EU, Art. 45-49 GDPR must be observed.

8.4. The Parties have appointed the following data protection officers:

For NCP

Name: XX

Contact: XX

For KOALA consortium

Name: XX

Contact: XX

8.5. In addition, the Contracting Parties undertake to comply with the current state of the art regarding data security.

9. Liability

9.1. The Parties shall carry out the work assumed by them under this Agreement properly and to the best of their knowledge, considering the state of the art in science and technology. As soon as one of the Parties becomes aware of any mismanagements, it shall inform the other Party without undue delay thereof.

9.2. Claims against each other for compensation of damages shall be excluded unless they are based on intent or gross negligence. This shall also apply to indirect damage. Liability for personal injury shall be governed by the statutory provisions.

9.3. In relation to third Parties, each Party shall be liable exclusively for itself and not for the other Party, to the extent that it is responsible for the damage. The Parties agree that, when exposed to claims by third Parties, they shall, in relation to each other, be liable only in accordance with their share of fault and shall, in each case, undertake to indemnify the other Party against further-reaching claims.

9.4. In the course of the cooperation, the Parties shall transmit information with the care customary in their own affairs. The Parties shall not be liable for the correctness and completeness of the information transmitted by them under this Agreement or for damages of any kind arising from the utilisation of this information, either during the duration of the cooperation or after the end of this Agreement. This shall be without prejudice to the terms set out in the sections above.

10. General Terms

10.1. The Agreement is confidential and should only be shared internally unless both Parties agree otherwise.

10.2. The invalidity of a provision of this Agreement shall be without prejudice to the validity of the remaining provisions of this Agreement. Rather, this provision shall be replaced with retroactive effect by a provision that is legally permissible and comes closest in its content to the original provision.

10.3. No Party shall be entitled to assume obligations with effect for the other Party without their prior express written consent.

10.4. The place of jurisdiction shall be XX/Germany. Applicable law shall be the law of the Federal Republic of Germany to the exclusion of the conflict of laws rules of private international law and of the UN Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods (CISG).

10.5. The Parties consent to execution and delivery of the Agreement electronically.

10.6. Any amendments and supplements to this Agreement shall require written form to be effective; the written form may be replaced by an electronic signed text document. This shall also apply to the waiver of the formal requirement.

For KOALA consortium

XX
XX

For NCP

XXX
XXX